

NOTES

The bands in the region 220–280 nm which appear both in the case of the ligands and the complexes, are attributed as π - π^* benzenoid bands³.

TABLE I

Complexes	Decomposition temp. (°C)	% of Pb		% of N	
		Calc.	Found	Calc.	Found
1. ϕ_2 Pb(L _I)	235	33.01	32.92	4.47	4.37
2. ϕ_2 Pb(L _{II}) (orange yellow)	232	30.67	30.41	4.15	4.08
3. ϕ_2 Pb(L _{III})	—	„	30.05	„	4.25
4. ϕ_2 Pb(L _{IV})	205	„	31.09	„	4.22
5. ϕ_2 Pb(L _V) (melts)	177	31.71	32.05	4.29	4.20
6. ϕ_2 Pb(L _{VI})	224	27.57	27.29	3.73	3.69
7. ϕ_2 Pb.2(L _{VII})	234	27.50	27.57	3.72	3.85
8. ϕ_2 Pb.2(L _{VIII})	201	26.43	26.98	3.58	3.61
9. ϕ_2 Pb.2(L _{IX})	176	24.62	25.45	3.33	3.50

In the i.r. all the ligands show absorption bands in the region 2800–2600 cm^{-1} , due to the presence of intramolecular H-bonded OH groups and around 1280 cm^{-1} due to the phenolic C–O stretching frequency. No such bands are shown by the complexes. Furthermore, the C = N stretching frequency of the ligands in the region 1640 cm^{-1} are shifted by 15–20 cm^{-1} in the cases of the complexes. These show the participation of the azomethine groups and the phenolic (–OH) groups of the ligands in the complex formation.

Further work to establish the probable structure of these complexes and also on the reaction of these types of Schiff bases and other nitrogen-containing ligands with diphenyl-lead dihalides is in progress and the results will be communicated in due course.

References

1. S. N. PODDAR, C. JAMES and N. S. DAS, Proceedings of the Convention of Chemists, C.S.I.R. (India), 1971, p. 40.
2. BARBIERI, BIANCA and RIVAROLA, *Z. anorg. allg. Chem.*, 1972, B387, 126.
3. K. CHATTERJEE and B. DOUGLAS, *Spectro. Chem. Acta.*, 1965, 21, 1625.

Studies on Some 4(7)-Iodobenzimidazoles

K. D. BANERJI & K. K. SEN

Department of Chemistry, Bhagalpur University, Bhagalpur-7

Manuscript received 31 October 1972; revised 12 February 1973; accepted 27 April 1973

IN view of very few iodobenzimidazoles reported so far¹, it was considered worthwhile to prepare a few 4(7)-iodobenzimidazoles. These were prepared from the corresponding diamines, reported by us

earlier. With formic and acetic acid, high yields of benzimidazoles were obtained (*vide exptl.*) but with a few other acids e.g., propionic, valeric, phenylacetic, chloroacetic and *p*-methoxyphenylthioglycolic acids evolution of vapours of iodine was observed indicating decomposition and pure iodobenzimidazoles could not be isolated. Condensation with amides also failed. Potassium ethyl xanthate, however, condensed smoothly to give the iodobenzimidazole in high yield.

The IR spectra of the compounds prepared agreed well with those of halobenzimidazoles².

Experimental

4(7)-Iodo- and 2-Methyl-4(7)-iodobenzimidazole :

The following adaptation of Phillip's method was used :

3-Iodo-*o*-phenylenediamine (0.02 mole), organic acid (0.1 mole) and 4(*N*)HCl (2.3 ml) were refluxed for 45 min, then diluted with water, cooled and neutralised with ammonia. The optd. solid was filtered, washed and recrystallised. 4(7)-Iodobenzimidazole (76%), violetish white needles (ethanol), m.p. 191°–92°. Lit.⁶ m.p. 188–189°.

$\text{C}_7\text{H}_5\text{IN}_2$ requires C—34.5, H—2.1%
Found C—34.6, H—1.9%.

2-Methyl-4(7)-iodobenzimidazole (64%), cream coloured needles (ethanol), m.p. 185°–187°.

$\text{C}_8\text{H}_7\text{IN}_2$ requires C—37.2, H—2.7%
Found C—36.9, H—2.9%.

2-Mercapto-4(7)-iodobenzimidazole :

The Procedure given in Organic Synthesis⁹ was followed. Yield 80%, light yellow shining needles, m.p. 277°–78°(d).

$\text{C}_7\text{H}_5\text{IN}_2\text{S}$ requires C—30.4, H—1.8%
Found C—30.8, H—2.1%.

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (K.K.S.) wishes to thank the U.G.C. for financial assistance.

References

1. J. R. R. HOOVER and A. R. DAY, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 77, 4324, 5652.
2. R. M. ACHESON, G. A. TAYLOR and M. L. TOMLINSON, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, 3750.
3. D. B. M. SCOTT, M. L. ROYER and C. ROSE, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, 80, 2165.
4. H. M. KISSMAN, R. G. CHILD and M. S. WEISS, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, 79, 1185; H. B. GILLESPIE, M. ENGLMAN, F. SPANO and S. CRAFF, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, 79, 2245; W. R. STEGART and A. R. DAY, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, 79, 4391; D. JERCHELL, German Pat. 888,032, 27 Aug. 1953; *Chem. Abs.*, 1958, 52, 348; Merch & Co., Brit. Pat. 783,306, 18 Sept. 1957, *Chem. Abs.*, 1957, 51, 10497.
5. J. J. LEAVITT, U.S. Pat. 2,773,896, 11 Dec. 1956; 2,793,192, 21 May 1957; *Chem. Abs.* 1957, 51, 4726, 13411; T. W. PFIRRMANN, German Pat. 811,122, 16 Aug. 1951. *Chem. Abs.*, 1954, 48, 9735.

6. (a) E. C. FISHER and M. M. JOULLIE, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1958, **23**, 1944; (b) *J. Org. Chem.*, 1961, **26**(i), 1649.
 7. S. K. GUHA, K. D. BANERJI and K. K. SEN, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1971, **48**, 1011.
 8. D. J. RABIGER and M. M. JOULLIE, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1964, 915.
 9. *Org. Synthesis*, Collective Volume IV, 1963, p. 569.

Spectrophotometric Studies of the Chelates of Copper(II) with 2-Hydroxy-5-methyl Acetophenonesemicarbazone

J. R. SHAH & R. P. PATEL

Department of Chemistry, Sardar Patel University, Vallabh Vidhyanagar

Manuscript received 23 December 1972; accepted 26 May 1973

SPECTROPHOTOMETRIC studies on complex formation in iron(III)-2-hydroxy-5-methyl acetophenone semicarbazone (5MeOAS) system have been reported earlier¹. The present communication describes the spectrophotometric study of green coloured complex formed by copper(II) and 5MeOAS.

Experimental and Results

5MeOAS was prepared as described earlier¹. Technical grade methanol was used after drying over anhydrous calcium chloride and then distilled. The stock solution of copper sulphate was prepared by dissolving a calculated amount of copper sulphate, the concentration of which was determined by standard gravimetric and volumetric methods.

Spectrophotometric measurements were made on Zeiss-specol using 1 cm matched cells. All measurements were carried out at $30^{\circ} \pm 1^{\circ}$ in a 50% methanol—50% water (by volume) medium.

The method of Vosburgh and Cooper² was employed to determine the nature of complexes. Mixtures containing 1 : 1, 1 : 2, and 1 : 3 mole-ratios of iron(III) to 5MeOAS were prepared. Absorbance measurements were carried out between 400 nm and 750 nm. The observations showed the presence of only one complex with $\lambda_{max} = 640$ nm formed in the system.

The composition of the complex was determined by three different methods, Job's³ using equimolar solutions, slope-ratio⁴ and mole-ratio⁵ methods. It was found to be 1 : 1 in all the three cases.

Effect of variation of pH on the degree of complex formation was studied. The optimum pH-range was observed to be 3.8 to 6.5 in which the complex was stable for several days.

The apparent stability constant, $\log K = 4.7 \pm 0.1$ of the complex was calculated from the absorbance data by the method of Mukherji and Dey.⁶

References

1. J. R. SHAH and R. P. PATEL, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.* (in press).
2. W. C. VOSBURGH and G. R. COOPER, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, **63**, 427.
3. P. JOB, *Ann. Chim.*, 1928, **9**, 113.
4. A. E. HARVEY and D. L. MANNING, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, **72**, 4488.
5. J. H. YOE and A. L. JONES, *Ind. Eng. Chem., Anal. Ed.*, 1924, **16**, 111.
6. A. K. MUKHERJI and A. K. DEY, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1958, **6**, 314.

Synthesis of 5,7,8-Trimethoxy-3-methylchromone derivatives

Y. A. SHAIKH & K. N. TRIVEDI

Chemistry Department, Faculty of Science, Baroda-2

Manuscript received 12 February 1973; accepted 10 May 1973

BENZO- γ -PYRONES or chromones having hydroxy or methoxy substituents in 5,7,8-positions are of interest as they are found in a great variety of compounds. Wiley¹ synthesised several chromones, which are found to have bronchodilator activity. We report here the synthesis of polymethoxy chromone derivatives, as this type of compounds, not only occur in nature but possess valuable therapeutic properties.

1,2,3,5-Tetramethoxy benzene², on Friedel-Crafts propionylation with propionic anhydride and anhydrous aluminium chloride afforded 2-hydroxy-3,4,6-trimethoxy propiophenone³ (I), which when subjected to Kostanecki-Robinson acylation with acetic anhydride and freshly fused sodium acetate, yielded a product, which was insoluble in alkali. The I.R. spectrum of the product showed a strong band in the carbonyl region viz., 1660 cm^{-1} (γ -pyronyl C = O group). It has been assigned 5,7,8-trimethoxy-2,3-dimethylchromone⁴ structure (IIa).

I

II

a : R = $-\text{CH}_3$

b : R = $-\text{C}_6\text{H}_5$

Kostanecki-Robinson benzoylation of compound(I), with benzoic anhydride and sodium benzoate afforded 5,7,8-trimethoxy-3-methylflavone(IIb). The I.R. Spectrum of (IIb) showed a strong band in the carbonyl region viz., 1600 cm^{-1} (γ -pyronyl C = O group) and did not develop any colouration with alcoholic ferric-chloride solution.